

Notes

Gluconate Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

C. PANDA and R. K. PATNAIK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College,
Rourkela-769 008

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REVIEW¹ and earlier investigations²⁻⁵ indicated the formation of 1 : 1 cobalt and nickel gluconate complexes and a precipitate above pH 7.0.

Since the formation of different complexes, their dissociation at different pH and determination of the dissociation constants were not done, we felt it worthwhile to study these aspects by pH measurement method.

Experimental

The pH measurements are carried out at 32°. Since the reactions are found to be slow, the solutions are stored for 48 hr in glass stoppered bottles for the pH measurements.

Fig. 1 : NaOH added in ml. ($\frac{M}{10}$)

Fig. 1 : pH titration of 50.0 ml. of solution containing 6.25×10^{-4} g. moles of gluconic acid and 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of sodium perchlorate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole of cobalt perchlorate (Curve B) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

Fig. 2 NaOH added in ml. ($\frac{M}{10}$)

Fig. 2 : pH titration of 50.0 ml. of solution containing 6.25×10^{-4} g mole of gluconic acid and 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of sodium perchlorate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole of nickel sulphate (Curve B) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

Discussions

The reaction taking place due to the interaction of metal ions with gluconic acid can be represented as

It can be shown as in the cadmium citrate complex⁶ that

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - a/b \Delta[TGl]}{[C]} = n - a/b \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } a = \frac{k}{[H^+]} \text{ and } b = 1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}$$

k is the dissociation constant of gluconic acid⁷ ($k = 2.75 \times 10^{-4}$). n values are calculated as before and are found to be greater than one beyond pH 4.5 for both cobalt and nickel systems.

Assuming n to be one below pH 4.5, the values of $[C^+]$ are calculated. The values of the equilibrium constant K of the reaction (1), calculated as followed in the cadmium citrate complex⁶, are found to be, 0.93×10^{-3} , 1.36×10^{-2} , 0.86×10^{-2} and 1.22×10^{-2} at pH 3.0, 3.2, 3.5 and 3.75 respectively for cobalt and 1.39×10^{-2} , 1.09×10^{-2} , 1.38×10^{-2} and 2.45×10^{-2} at pH 3.75, 4.0, 4.25 and 4.50 respectively for nickel system. The mean values of K are 1.09×10^{-2} and 1.58×10^{-2} for cobalt and nickel systems respectively.

In the pH range 4.75–7.50 in the case of cobalt and 4.75–7.00 in the case of nickel systems, the values of n are greater than one and less than two. So in these pH ranges, the complex C^+ dissociates to a neutral complex C and a proton according to the reaction,

It can be shown as in the cadmium citrate complex⁶ that

$$K_1 = \frac{[C][H^+]}{[C^+]} = \frac{(n-1)[H^+]}{(2-n)} \quad (4)$$

K_1 values thus calculated are 6.00×10^{-8} , 4.04×10^{-8} , 2.30×10^{-8} and 1.32×10^{-8} at pH 6.00, 6.25, 6.5 and 6.75 respectively for cobalt gluconate and 7.48×10^{-8} , 5.02×10^{-8} , 3.39×10^{-8} and 2.17×10^{-8} at pH 6.25, 6.5, 6.75 and 7.00 respectively for nickel gluconate complex.

Cobalt and nickel gluconates are precipitated above pH 7.5 and 7.0 respectively. The cobalt and nickel contents of these precipitates, estimated by pyridine thiocyanate method, are found to be 23.13% and 23.07% respectively, which corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 metal gluconate complex.

Fig. 3 : pH titration of 50.0 ml. of solution containing 6.25×10^{-4} g. mole of sodium gluconate and 5.0×10^{-8} g. mole sodium perchlorate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole of cobalt perchlorate (Curve B) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

Fig. 4 : pH titration of 50.0 ml. of solution containing 6.25×10^{-4} g. mole of sodium gluconate and 5.0×10^{-8} g. mole of sodium perchlorate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole nickel sulphate (Curve B) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

The complexes C^+ and C are present in the pH ranges 4.5–7.5 and 4.5–7.0 for cobalt and nickel systems respectively in experiments 3 and 4.

It can be shown as in the manganese tartrate⁸ complex that

$$[C] = [H^+] + [NaOH] + \frac{[TGI]_B - [Metal\ salt]}{b} \quad (5)$$

K_1 values calculated as before are found to be 1.19×10^{-8} , 1.29×10^{-8} and 1.41×10^{-8} at pH 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3 respectively for cobalt and 1.1×10^{-8} , 1.25×10^{-8} and 1.5×10^{-8} at pH 6.90, 6.95 and 7.00 respectively for nickel system. The mean values of K_1 are 1.29×10^{-8} and 1.28×10^{-8} for cobalt and nickel systems respectively which are in good agreement with the results obtained in the experiments 1 and 2.

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References

1. D. T. SAWYER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 64, 633.
2. V. K. ZOLUTUKHIN, S. V. LINOK, N. I. VERBYLAN and S. I. BALABAS, *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 59, 2372.
3. W. F. PICKERING and J. F. ASHTON, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1970, 23, 1367.
4. L. G. JOYCE and W. F. PICKERING, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1965, 18, 783.
5. G. A. MELSON and W. F. PICKERING, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 1205.
6. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 673.
7. R. K. CANNAN and A. KIBRICK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2314.
8. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 511.

Complex Compounds of Bi- and Tri-Valent Silver

A. K. BANERJEE* and S. P. GHOSH

Chemistry Department, Patna University, Patna 800 005

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THOUGH Silver (II) exhibits a strong oxidising property, still the higher oxidation state of silver has been stabilised by co-ordination with many nitrogen containing heterocyclic bases¹. The oxidation potential of Ag (I) to Ag (II) is rather high, being 1.914 volts in nitric acid solution and 1.41 volts in alkaline solution, but these values are considerably lowered by co-ordination. Further all the complexes are very insoluble in aqueous medium; as such even in presence of these strongly oxidising agents, number of these complexes have been synthesised fairly easily.

In the present communication, the preparation and properties of a few complexes of Ag(II) with *p*-phenetylbisguanide and Ag(III) with 2-guanidinobenzimidazole molecule have been described.

* To whom all correspondence should be made